

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B202
Date: 23 May 2006
Take Off 09:56:25
Landing: 14:43:37
Flight Time 4h47m12s

Campaign: ICEPIC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: SW

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Clare Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	Mission Scientist 2	Alan Blyth	Leeds University
8	CPI	Hazel Jones	Manchester University
9	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Bob Wells	FAAM
10	MARSS	Dave Pollard	Met Office
11	CCN	Bruce Giddings	Met Office
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B202 Track 23-MAY-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b202
 Date: 23/5/06
 Project: ICEPIC
 Location: SW approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093910		inu to nav	0.33 kft	125	
093942		engine start	0.33 kft	125	
094417		taxy	0.33 kft	125	start
095625		T/O	0.32 kft	212	from Cranfield
100030		asp open	6.5 kft	070	
100842		jw/nevz zero	10.0 kft	247	
103900		camera	20.0 kft	240	start ffc, dfc
104051	110114	Profile 1	20.0 - -.04 kft	241	
105544		Profile 1	4.0 kft	254	interrupt
105649		Profile 1	4.0 kft	127	resume
110114	111122	Run 1	-.04 - 0.04 kft	045	
111326	111449	Profile 2	0.03 - 1.4 kft	225	
111544	112546	Run 2	1.2 - 0.96 kft	228	qnh 1016
112645	112955	Profile 3	0.99 - 4.0 kft	139	
112955	113038	Run 3	4.0 kft	139	
113226	113519	Run 4	4.0 kft	149	
113754	114124	Run 5	5.0 kft	331	
114345	114624	Run 6	6.5 kft	177	
114812	115116	Run 7	7.4 kft	323	
115315	115508	Run 8	8.0 kft	166	
115703	115937	Run 9	8.5 - 8.6 kft	320	
120220	120419	Run 10	9.0 kft	163	
120643	120843	Run 11	9.5 kft	310	
121139	121402	Run 12	10.0 kft	226	
122900	123118	Run 13	4.0 - 5.5 kft	289	
123322	123825	Run 14	5.5 kft	058	
124049	124516	Run 15	6.5 kft	253	
125219	125646	Run 16	7.5 kft	051	
125845	130258	Run 17	8.0 kft	237	
131349	131812	Run 18	4.0 kft	087	
132102	132504	Run 19	6.0 kft	281	
132955	133458	Run 20	8.0 kft	118	
134450	134921	Run 21	8.5 kft	077	
135614	135914	Run 22	9.0 kft	332	
144337		Land	0.31 kft	213	
144704		standstill	0.33 kft	308	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B202 Track 23-MAY-06

Flight No: B202

Date: 23rd May 2006

Trial objectives:

To investigate the development of ice-phase and precipitation in Cu over the UK.

Location:

In developing Cu clouds over SW / Central S.England or Wales (NOTAM area A/B)

Weather:

Either individual, or groups of Cu cloud forming predominantly over land. Evolving clouds may also be tracked over the sea. If suitable clouds are also growing over the sea, these may also be sampled.

Special requirements:

Key temperature levels for cloud penetrations are 0, -3, -6, -9C then colder as reqd. If operating near Chilbolton radar, relay range/bearing of target clouds to "Radsearch" (130.575 MHz). Maintain continuous monitoring of turbulence probe differential pressures – if any icing observed, descend below freezing level to clear.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 10:00L.
2. Transit to the operating region at FL200 and identify suitable clouds (40mins).
3. Perform profile descent from FL200 to minimum permitted altitude at 1000ft/minute (70mins). May be stepped to avoid cloud penetrations. Profile ideally finishes below target clouds.
4. Perform a SLR below cloud for 10minutes in a direction determined by the mission scientist to remain in inflow of target clouds (85mins).
5. Turn onto reciprocal heading and perform a SLR at 500ft below cloudbase for ten minutes (100mins).
6. Ascend to around the 0C level or 500ft below the cloud top (110mins).
7. Perform a penetration with wings level through the cloud (115mins).
8. If a single cloud is large and clearly identifiable and the cloud is continuing to develop, make a reciprocal turn while ascending by ~1000ft (-3C in temperature) and repeat the cloud penetration several times (150mins).
9. If the cloud is not large or discrete, then proceed successively to the next visible cumulus cell, and repeat the penetrations at approximately 0C for a 10minute interval. Perform reciprocal turn while climbing by intervals of -3C and repeat 10minute runs (150mins).
10. Continue 8 and/or 9 as time permits (250mins).
11. Finish with a profile ascent from minimum permitted altitude to FL200 or 1000ft above highest cumulus tops (whichever is higher) at 1000ft/min.
12. Transit to Cranfield and land (300mins).

Note) – target clouds should be continuing to develop – look for rising cloud tops and solid, sharp-edged cloud boundaries. If red echoes show on the aircraft radar, or cloud top is decreasing, or cloud becomes heavily glaciated (diffuse boundaries) then move on to next cloud

Mission Scientist Debrief

B202 - 23/05/06

ICEPIC flight over the West Country

Mission scientist – Clare Lee

Weather conditions

Westerly wind, with convective activity over the sea and land for most of the South West of the country. Over the land the convective cells were capping around –12 degrees. Some cirrus was present during the transit, but generally clear above the Cu cells in the operating area.

Sortie

After the transit, the area of operation was entered at FL200 enabling a good view of the operating area. A profile descent to 50ft was made to the West, towards the air upstream of the operating area. This profile was over the sea and interrupted to avoid cloud during the descent. It was immediately followed by a 100ft run below the cloud, reciprocal to the majority of the profile. A profile climb was made to 1500ft, followed by a reciprocal run at 1000ft remaining below the cloud. Cloud bases were estimated to be at 1500ft. Some of the more developed Cu were seen to be precipitating in the distance. At the end of the run a particularly good cell was identified to study. A profile was made to the freezing layer (4000ft), immediately followed by a run towards the cloud. Unfortunately due to air traffic restrictions the immediate area of operation had to be changed and a new cell was identified over the land. A straight and level run through the cloud was flown at 4000ft (temp ~ 0deg). A series of climbs and turns followed by straight and level runs through the cloud were performed. The Cu cell top ascended quite slowly so typically increments of 500ft were made up to 10000ft. The turbulence probes showed signs of icing and so a descent was made to 3000ft to deice. Note that it took longer to deice than has previously been experienced in other flights.

After de-icing a new young cell was identified. A run at the freezing layer (4000ft) was made through the cloud. A series of climbs and turns followed by straight and level runs were made through a few neighbouring clouds. At 8000ft the turbulence probes again showed signs of icing and a descent to 3000ft was made.

A new isolate large cell with two clumps was identified. Straight and level runs were again performed with climbs and turns to re-penetrate the cloud at several levels from 4000ft to 8000ft. At 8000ft the turbulence probes again showed signs of icing so a descent was made to 3000ft. On de-icing a climb to 8500ft was flown to penetrate the same cloud. At the end of this run the probes iced again and hence another manoeuvre to 3000ft was made, this time followed by a climb to 9000ft for another run through the same cloud. Towards the end of the run at 9000ft the probes iced again and the end of science was declared rather than de-icing the probes again.

Instrument problems

Cloud physics – occasionally extra noisy on the PCASP, otherwise all OK

MARSS – Channel 16 not working, otherwise OK

Nev – failed on final approach, but OK throughout science

Core instruments – turbulence probes – has excessive freezing, which could possibly be due to trapped water.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B202**. Date **23/5/06** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **1** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~0955					Take-off Cranfield.
		FZ100			flying along Daventry corridor
					618 W all around tops ~FZ70
102000		FZ200			For transit
					Clouds thickening to West.
					Both W + Ci
104051	P1 ↓	FZ200	241		Descending over sea.
					avoiding clouds by small adjustments
		11000			Inversion seen T = -15°C
					Winds 11ms ⁻¹ / 269°
105300		~6000			Tops of current W. ~6000ft.
105452		~5000			Small turbulence in clear, W W
					all around.
105544	P1 int.	4000ft			Interrupting profile to avoid
					cloud, turning left.
					T = 0°C, T _d = -2.53°C.
105649	P1 rec.	4000ft	104		Recommence profile.
	(P1 end.	50ft.	049		
110114	(R)	100ft.	045		
111030					Some rain
111222	R1 end				End of run.
					Turning left. for rejoin
					Run below cloud.
111326	P2 ↑	100ft.	225		Profile climb.
111449	P2 end	1500ft.			
111544	R2	1000ft.	227	51°12'N 4°24'W	QH 1016

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B202**..... Date **23/5/06**..... Name **CLARE LEE**..... Page **2** of **6**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Some of the W to right giving rain. Odd spot of rain on windscreens. Heading under young rain-precip W.
			237		Tanger clouds to S+W wind 8ms ⁻¹ / 259° T = 7.8°C, T _D = 3.74°C.
112546	R2end				Run end turning left towards good W side
112645	R3↑ § R3end	1000ft. 4000ft.	139		Profiling to freezing layer.
112955	R3				T = 0.57°C, T _D = -5°C
112955	R3end				Turning left due to air traffic.
113226	R4	4000ft.	149		Heading for different cloud (water part)
113430	R4end	4000ft.			In main part of cloud water drops only.
					Climbing to 5000ft. + right turn.
		5000ft.			T = -1.0°C, T _D = -5.11°C. In + at of cloud.
113754	R5	5000ft.	344		T = -1.9°C -5°C , T _D ~ -15°C. <small>Aircraft:</small> Radar showing precip. CP1 + 2D seeing large aggregates. Quite low turbulence.
114124	R5end	5000ft.	344		End run + right turn + climb to 6500ft. (~500ft below cloud top)
114345	R6				

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B202**... Date **23/5/06** Name **CUARE LEE**... Page **3** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
111500					In cloud.
					CPI + 2D seeing variety of particles (including columns, aggregates)
114624	R6end	6500ft.			End of run, left turn. + Climb to 7500ft.
					$T \sim -4^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_D \sim -12.8^{\circ}\text{C}$
114812	R7	7500ft.	323		$T = -5.86^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_D = -8.36^{\circ}\text{C}$ (out of cloud)
115030					Extending at into clear. so that after turn can also sample additional Cu cell off to left in next run.
115116	R7end	7500ft.	315		$T = -5.76$, $T_D = -10.8^{\circ}\text{C}$
					Climb to 8000ft. (-above most of Cu over sea.) left turn.
115315	R8	8000ft.	166		N.B. Original cloud topped at.
	R8end				End of run. + climb + left turn
		8500ft.			$T = -8.5^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_D = -9.73^{\circ}\text{C}$ at cloud.
					No Cu above
115703	R9	8500ft.	306		$T = -8.3^{\circ}\text{C}$ $T_D = -8.45^{\circ}\text{C}$
115957	R9end	8500ft.			End run, turning right.
120720	R10	9000ft.			$T = -8.91^{\circ}$, $T_D = -10.97^{\circ}\text{C}$
					Cu only ascending slowly.
120419	R10end	9000ft.			Turning left. + climb.
120643	R11	9500ft.	311.		Still in Cu tops, but cloud looks as if its starting to decay.
					$T = -10.21^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_D = -13.49^{\circ}\text{C}$.
120843	R11end	9500ft.			left turn + climb.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B202**.. Date **23/5/06**.. Name **CLARE LEE**..... Page **4** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121139	R12	FL100			Heading towards fresh ω cell protruding above stratus layer.
121402	R12end.				Descending to deice. (3000ft.)
121530		8000ft.			ω seeing steller plates as descending through a different cell.
		3000ft.			Staying at 3000ft. to deice ^{T = -3.2°C} probe.
122630					Climbing to 4000ft.
12	R13	4000ft.	289	30°24'N / 40°48'W	T = 1°C. ^{→ 0.8°C} T _D = -2.86°C.
					wind 11ms ⁻¹ more turbulent.
123118	R13end.	4000ft.	287		End run. left turn + climb.
123322	R14	5000ft.	59		Run near top cloud (500ft below?) T = -2.13°C, T _D = -3.5°C Some ice + water drops.
123627					larger ω ahead with precip below.
123825	R14end	5500ft.	098.		End run, left turn + climb.
124049	R15	6500ft.	252		
124516	R15end.				End of run + climb to γ Waiting to hear from Phil re. <u>Ullrich Horn</u> ^{the} _{answer}
125219	R16	7500ft.	051		New ω (500ft below top.) _{location.}
125646	R16end	7500ft.	052.		End run. left turn + climb. T = -6.77°C, T _D = -9.12°C.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.202**... Date **23/5/06**... Name **CLARE LEE**..... Page **5** of **6**.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125845	R17	8000ft.	237		Heading back through large cloud
130011					Slight turn to left for additional cloud.
	R17end	8000ft.			End run
		3000ft.			Descending to deice.
		4000ft.			Heading for new area.
					lining up to go along length - will penetrate 2 clumps.
131349	R18	4000ft.	290 090		$T = -0.12^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_D = -0.14^{\circ}\text{C}$. (in cloud) CPL + 2D seeing water + melting ice. $\frac{1}{2}$ over sea $\frac{1}{2}$ in over land.
131812	R18end	4000ft.			End run. Turn \rightarrow + climb.
		6000ft.			Manoeuvring to end of cloud again.
132102	R19	6000ft.	295		$T = -3.6^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_D = -3.4^{\circ}\text{C}$. <small>for reciprocal.</small>
132504	R19end	6000ft.			End run. Procedural turn + climb.
					Wind 7ms^{-1} 125°
					Cloud moving East.
132955	R20	8000ft.	118	$51^{\circ}0'N$ $4^{\circ}30'W$	Out of cloud.
					Heading towards same cell.
					$T = -6.54^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_D = -7.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.
133458	R20end	8000ft.			Need to deice again.
					Descending to 3000ft.
134026					Climbing again to 8500ft.
					to go back to original cell.
					Majority of cell tops \sim 6000ft
134450	R21	8500ft.	087		Heading towards same cell as before.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B202**... Date **23/5/06**.. Name **CLARE LEE**..... Page **6** of **6**..

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					T = -7.93°C, T _D = -7.94°C.
					Wind 16ms ⁻¹ 1232°
					CPI + 2D seeing ice. FSSP seeing some water drops.
134921	R2land	8500ft.			End run. Descending for deicing. Deiced at 3000ft. Ascending back up for run at 9000ft.
135614	R22	9000ft.	332		T = -8.2°C, T _D = -6.4°C
135850					Turbulence probes gone again.
135914	R2land	9000ft.			End of run. Ending science rather than deicing probes again.
		FL110			Transiting back. Still lots of W but not going high.
~ 1430					Land at Cranfield.
					Instrument status
					Cloud physics: All OK.
					Occasionally PCAASP noisy.
					CPI: OK.
					CCN: OK.
					MARSS: no ch16. Otherwise OK.
					Core: regular icing on attack turbulence probe - trapped water?
					Nav failed on final approach. Science OK though.

Aircraft FDR - long bit acceleration. - Request via Bob.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B202

Date: 23/05/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:40:51	Noise		14	1				Noise								Start Profile 1 from FL200	
10:42:01	Noise			1				Noise								FL190	
10:43:10	Noise			1				Noise								FL180	
10:44:10	Noise			1				Noise								FL170	
10:45:07	Noise			1												FL160	
10:45:58	200	0.08		1												FL150	
10:46:53	320	0.09		1												FL140	
10:47:48	220	0.09		2												FL130	
10:48:36	230	0.09		5												FL120	
10:49:35	270	0.09		3												FL110	
10:50:24	300	0.09		2												FL100	
10:51:19	Noise			2												FL090	
10:52:02	110	0.09		1												FL080	
10:52:54	145	0.08		1												FL070	
10:53:52	120	0.09		2												FL060	
10:54:41	145	0.09		5												FL050	
10:55:44	170	0.09		10												FL040	
10:57:37	150	0.10		10												FL030	
10:58:30	195	0.09		10												FL020	
10:59:25	135	0.09		10												FL010	
11:01:13	180	0.09		10												End of Profile 1 @ 50'	
11:01:22																Start Run 1 @ 100'	
11:02:00	150	0.10	15	20													
11:04:00	155	0.11		15													
11:06:00	150	0.10		20													
11:08:00	125	0.10		20													
11:10:00	110	0.11		20													
11:11:22																End of Run 1	
11:13:25	110	0.10		5												Start Profile 2 from 100'	
11:14:33	100	0.10		5												FL010	
11:14:50																End of Profile 2 @ FL012	
11:15:49																Start Run 2 @ 1000'	
11:16:00	105	0.09		10													
11:18:00	110	0.10		15													
11:20:00	145	0.10		15													
11:22:00	115	0.10		10													
11:24:00	150	0.10		15													
11:25:46																End of Run 2	
11:26:46	170	0.10		20												Start Profile 3 from 1000'	
11:27:49	Noise			20												FL020	
11:28:50	135	0.10		10												FL030	
11:29:56	100	0.10		10												End of Profile 3 @ FL040 & Start Run 3	
11:30:00	95	0.09		10													
11:30:45																Abort run due to traffic	
11:32:26																Start Run 4 @ FL040	
11:33:00	140	0.09	17	5													

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B202

Date: 23/05/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:35:00	120	0.09	34	5													
11:35:23																End of Run 4	
11:37:55																Start Run 5 @ FL050	
11:38:00	100	0.10	80	2													
11:40:00	500	0.13	133	1000		220	800	11000	1000						8		
11:41:25																End of Run 5	
11:43:44																Start Run 6 @ FL065	
11:44:00	280	0.10	151	2												PCASP a little noisy	
11:46:00	230	0.10	196	200		10	600								5		
11:46:25																End of Run 6	
11:48:12																Start Run 7 @ FL075	
11:49:00	580	0.16	201	1000		545	700	55000	3000						8		
11:51:17																End of Run 7	
11:53:16																Start Run 8 @ FL080	
11:54:00	1100	0.15	223	2000		1000	400	55000	200						10		
11:55:12																End of Run 8	
11:57:02																Start Run 9 @ FL085	
11:58:00	300	0.13	226	1000		1200	300	27000	400						10		
11:59:35																End of Run 9	
12:02:18																Start Run 10 @ FL090	
12:03:00	150	0.08	256	1000		20	375	16000	2000						8		
12:04:21																End of Run 10	
12:06:43																Start Run 11 @ FL095	
12:07:00	160	0.08	270	2													
12:08:45																End of Run 11	
12:11:37																Start Run 12 @ FL100	
12:12:00	130	0.08	281	5													
12:14:02																End of Run 12	
12:29:02																Start Run 13 @ FL040	
12:30:00	1400	0.11	384	1000		10	800	8	1000						1		
12:31:18																End of Run 13	
12:33:20																Start Run 14 @ FL055	
12:34:00	500	0.14	470	2000		140	800	23000	3000						8		
12:36:00	180	0.10	575	5													
12:38:00	1000	0.12	602	3000		300	800	1000	1200						8		
12:38:27																End of Run 14	
12:40:48																Start Run 15 @ FL065	
12:41:00	540	0.10	642	5													
12:43:00	1100	0.15	683	1500		225	800	1000	1000								
12:45:17																End of Run 15	
12:52:15																Start Run 16 @ FL075	
12:53:00	100	0.08	747	2500		1200	1000	70000	2000						5		
12:55:00	500	0.15	766	2000		300	400	1400	400						10		
12:56:45																End of Run16	
12:58:44																Start Run 17 @ FL080	
12:59:00	100	0.08	775	1000		2	200	20000	200						10		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B202**Date:**

23/05/2006

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B202_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B202_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	21/06/06	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B202 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B202_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown		Problems running this but Manually edited o/p file
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B202 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use, in order of preference, - if a calibration exists after the flight date, then the file that is closest in time to it, - or the most recent calibration file prior to the flight date. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	N 21/06/06	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL03052006.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B202_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B202_mfdX','pmsdata:B202_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	21/06/06	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto 4 secs manually added
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B202_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B202_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	21/06/06	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		Yes. FFSSP LWC good agreement with Nevz.LWC
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		
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CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B202

Date:

23/05/2006

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B202.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B202.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B202.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B202.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B202_seadas.dat iii) exit		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written 68011 blocks read / written No bad ones
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B202 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B202_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data N j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: N l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	21/06/06	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files. Not required Not required
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B202 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B202 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	095500 144800 10	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B202_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	21/0	Files in O:/Cloud Phys Core data
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO a) Flight number: B202 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B202_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B202_PROC2D	0 095500 144800 0.2 8 / 8 2 21/06/06	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end. Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. Note the particle type
10) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B202_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B202_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	21/06/06	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
11) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B202_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B202_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	21/06/06	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		Looks OK.

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

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E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC		
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults		Defaults in [square brackets]
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:B202_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B202.nc]		As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated
2) Ftp transfer to BADC		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B202.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B202.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B202_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary	21/06/06	COMPLETE

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:B202*.* outdir:B202_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.	21/06/06	Note destination directory "outdir" In CLOUD_PHYS:[BROWN.PMSZIP]

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B202**Date:**

23/05/2006

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC B202_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B202_FFSSP_HVMS.txt B202_FFSSP.raw B202_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B202_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS B202.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (B202.zip) - rename B202.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B202_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B202_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B202_rawseadas.zip	21/06/06	Binary data transfer Raw data already transferred to BADC from FAAM

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	23/05/06	Flight	B202	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	ICEPIC		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X
FERA on			at time	07:37:23		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	16.3°C	Ch	16.0°C	Ch18	14.7°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	07:37:59		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	286.7	Cold	285.7		
Target heating						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	07:40:28		
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual	X

Deimos NOT OPERATED

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	08:52:16		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.65	Cold	289.4	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	N/A	35.44	38.33	40.87	42.56	

Power changeover

Headset on before start					
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.				
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)					
Exit Deimos Software (x)					
POWER CHANGEOVER					
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton				
Restart Deimos Software					
System running again				at time	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 202** Date: 23rd May 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	N
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	N	Racks:	
FWVS	N	INC	N
<u>Radiometers</u>		CCN / CPC	Y
Upper Clear	Y	CVI	N
“ Red	Y		
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
		AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
IR Camera			
TAFTS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
MARSS	Y	AVAPS	N
DEIMOS	n	IR Camera	N
ARIES	n	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	n	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B202

Date: 23rd May 2006

Instruments

1. Turbulence probe iced up repeatedly, 5 times in all, in pretty tame icing conditions, SAT around minus 8C. Each time necessitated a descent to the freezing level to clear.
2. Nevz failed during final approach, revived following switch on/off.

Aircraft

Satcom Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B202:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	NO log taken - replaced by post flight auto cal removal
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	26 Sep 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

3 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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